

ANNOTATED LIST OF FISHES OF THE CHIRCHIK RIVER, UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *A list of fish inhabiting the water bodies of the Chirchik river basin is given. The list contains 43 species belonging to 8 orders, 15 families, and 38 genera. Included are all currently registered species whose validity has been revised in the relevant systematic revisions. The results of ichthyological observations along the Chirchik River for 1996-2021 are presented. The list of species is provided using international ichthyological norms and international databases. Coordinate addresses were obtained and a Geo information system map was created.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, River Chirchik, Ichthyofauna, species composition, native species, Alien species, Climatised species, coordinates.*

Introduction: Research of the ichthyofauna of Central Asia, in particular Uzbekistan, began in the 18th-19th century by expeditions of travelers A.P. Fedchenko and N.M. Prezhevalsky. Below is a taxonomic list of 43 fish species found in the River Chirchik. Classification of taxa from class to genus is given according to the system of J. Nelson (Nelson, 2006; Nelson *et al.*, 2016) with minor changes (Eshmeyer, 1990; Annotated catalog, 1998; Atlas of Russian freshwater fish, 2002; Bogutskaya and Naseka, 2004; Kottelat, 2012; Prokofiev, 2017; Mirzaev, 2000, 2001, 2019; Mirzaev and Quvatov, 2020; Kamilov *et al.*, 2004), compared with data from the international fish database (Froese R. and Pauly D. 2022).

Studies on the study of biology, identification and description, morphometry, morphology of fish species were also given in the works of scientists from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), G.V. Nikolsky (Nikolsky, 1971, 1974), F.A. Turdakov (Turdakov, 1963), V.P. Mitrafanov *et. all.* (Mitrafanov *et all.*, 1989), A.N. Reshetnikov (Reshetnikov, 2018), M.F. Wundzettel (Wundzettel, 2006), A.M. Prokofev (Prokofev, 2010).

Thanks to the work of G.K. Kamilov (Kamilov, 1973), T.V. Salikhov (Salikhov, 1990), U.T. Mirzaev (Mirzaev, 2000, 2001) information on the ichthyofauna of the River Chirchik has expanded significantly, but complete faunistic lists of fish species have not yet been published.

Material and Methods: Some data on the composition of the ichthyofauna are given with amendments and additions based on the study of the material by U.T. Mirzaev, collected in 1996-2018. In recent years (2019-2021) A.Q. Quvatov, ichthyological materials were collected (Fig. 1). Collections of which were processed and published by K.F. Kessler (Kessler, 1872, 1874, 1877) and S.M. Gertsenstein (Gertsenstein, 1888). The first, most complete information about the fish found in the River Chirchik is given in the works of L.S. Berg (Berg, 1905, 1948, 1949), G.V. Nikolsky (Nikolsky, 1938), F.A. Turdakov (Turdakov, 1963).

Fig. 1. As a result of ichthyological research conducted along the Chirchik River during 2019-2021, the meeting places of fish species collected are listed.

Results:

The list of modern ichthyofauna of fish species distributed in the Chirchik River and its tributaries is presented in **Table 1**.

Table-1

Current modern ichthyofauna of Chirchik River water bodies

№	In the section of family and species	Mountain zone	Foothill zone	Plain zone	Lower zone
Cyprinidae					
1	<i>Rhodeus ocellatus</i>	-	-	AI	-
2	<i>Luciobarbus conocephalus</i>	-	-	E	E
3	<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	-	-	A	A
4	<i>Hemiculter leucisculus</i>	AI	AI	-	-
5	<i>Carassius gibelio</i>	-	-	A	A
6	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	N	N	N	N
7	<i>Abbottina rivularis</i>	-	-	AI	AI
8	<i>Gobio cynocephalus</i>	-	-	AI	-
9	<i>Gobio lepidolaemus</i>	-	E	E	-
10	<i>Pseudorasbora parva</i>	-	-	AI	-
11	<i>Abramis brama orientalis</i>	-	-	-	E
12	<i>Alburnoides taeniatus</i>	-	-	E	-
13	<i>Alburnus oblongus</i>	-	-	E	-
14	<i>Aristichthys nobilis</i>	-	-	A	A
15	<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i>	-	-	A	A
16	<i>Aspius aspius iblioides</i>	-	-	-	E
17	<i>Squalius squaliusculus</i>	-	-	-	E
18	<i>Rutilus aralensis</i>	-	-	E	E
19	<i>Pelecus cultratus</i>	-	-	A	A
20	<i>Opsariichthys bidens</i>	-	-	AI	-
21	<i>Gymnodiptychus kessleri</i>	N	-	-	-
22	<i>Schizothorax eurystomus</i>	E	E	E	E
Cobitidae					
23	<i>Sabanejewia aralensis</i>	-	-	E	-
Balitoridae					
24	<i>Iskandaria kuschakewitschi</i>	-	E	E	-
25	<i>Triplophysa coniptera salari</i>	-	-	E	E
26	<i>Triplophysa dorsalis</i>	-	E	-	-
27	<i>Triplophysa elegans</i>	-	E	E	-
28	<i>Triplophysa strauchi</i>	-	-	-	AI
Ictaluridae					
29	<i>Ictalurus punctatus</i>	-	-	-	A
Siluridae					
30	<i>Siluris glanis</i>	-	-	N	N
Sisoridae					
31	<i>Glyptosternon oschanini</i>	E	-	-	-

Esocidae					
32	<i>Esox Lucius</i>	-	-	N	N
Coregonidae					
33	<i>Coregonus peled</i>	A	-	-	-
Salmonidae					
34	<i>Parasalmo mykiss</i>	A	-	-	-
35	<i>Salmo ischchan</i>	A	-	-	-
Adrianichthyidae					
36	<i>Oryzias sinensis</i>	-	-	AI	AI
Poecilidae					
37	<i>Gambusia affinis</i>	-	-	A	A
38	<i>Gambusia holbrooki</i>	-	-	A	A
Cottidae					
39	<i>Cottus jaxartensis</i>	E	-	-	-
Percidae					
40	<i>Sander lucioperca</i>	-	-	-	A
Odontobutidae					
41	<i>Micropercops cinctus</i>	-	-	AI	AI
Gobiidae					
42	<i>Rhinogobius brunneus</i>	-	-	AI	AI
Channidae					
43	<i>Channa argus</i>	-	-	AI	AI
	Total:	9	7	29	25
	Endemic species:	16			
	Native species:	4			
	Acclimatized species:	12			
	Alien introduced species:	11			

Note: E – Endemic species, N – Native species, A – Acclimatized species, AI – Alien introduced species.

Below is a list of species recorded in Chirchik River water bodies based on modern systematics and taxonomic nomenclature.

Chordata

Vertebrata

Osteichthyes

Actinopterygii Klein, 1885

Neopterygii

Teleostei

Euteleostei

Ostariophysii

Cypriniformes

Cyprinidae Fleming, 1822**Acheilognathinae** Bleeker, 1863**Rhodeus** (Agassiz, 1832)

1. *Rhodeus ocellatus* (Kner, 1866)

Barbinae (Bleeker, 1859)**Luciobarbus** (Heckel, 1843)

2. *Luciobarbus conocephalus* (Kessler, 1872)

Squaliobarbinae (Rainboth, 1991)**Ctenopharyngodon** (Steindachner, 1866)

3. *Ctenopharyngodon idella* (Valenciennes, 1844)

Cultrinae (Nikolsky, 1950)**Hemiculter** (Bleeker, 1859)

4. *Hemiculter leucisculus* (Basilewsky, 1855)

Cyprininae (Bonaparte, 1831)**Carassius** (Jarocki, 1822)

5. *Carassius gibelio* (Bloch, 1782)

Cyprinus (Linnaeus, 1758)

6. *Cyprinus carpio* (Linnaeus, 1759)

Gobioninae (Jordan et Fowler, 1803)**Abbottina** (Jordan et Fowler, 1903)

7. *Abbottina rivularis* (Basilewsky, 1855)

Gobio (Cuvier, 1816)

8. *Gobio cynocephalus* (Dybowski 1869)

9. *Gobio lepidolaemus* (Kessler, 1872)

Pseudorasbora (Bleeker, 1859)

10. *Pseudorasbora parva* (Temminck et Schlegel, 1846)

Leuciscinae (Bonaparte, 1837)**Abramidini** (Dybowski, 1862)**Abramis** (Cuvier, 1816)

11. *Abramis brama* (Linnaeus, 1758) *ssp. orientalis* (Berg, 1949)

Alburnini (Girard, 1859)**Alburnoides** (Jetteles, 1861)

12. *Alburnoides taeniatus* (Kessler, 1874)

Alburnus (Rafinesque, 1820)

13. *Alburnus oblongus* (Bulgakov, 1923)

Hypophthalmichthyini (Günther, 1868)**Aristichthys** (Oshima, 1919)

14. *Aristichthys nobilis* (Richardson, 1845)

Hypophthalmichthys (Bleeker, 1859)

15. *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* (Valenciennes, 1844)

Leuciscini (Bonaparte, 1846)

Aspius (Agassiz, 1832)

16. *Aspius aspius* (Linnaeus, 1758) *ssp. iblioides* (Kessler, 1872)

Squalius (Bonaparte, 1837)

17. *Squalius squaliusculus* (Kessler, 1872)

Rutilus (Rafinesque, 1820)

18. *Rutilus aralensis* (Berg, 1916)

Pelecinae (Bogutskaya, 1990)

Pelecus (Agassiz, 1835)

19. *Pelecus cultratus* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Rasborinae (Günther, 1868)

Opsariichthys (Bleeker, 1863)

20. *Opsariichthys bidens* (Günther, 1873)

Schizothoracinae

Gymnodiptychus (Herzenstein, 1892)

21. *Gymnodiptychus kessleri* (Russky, 1888)

Schizothorax (Heckel, 1838)

22. *Schizothorax eurystomus* (Kessler, 1872)

Cobitoidea (Swainson, 1839) (emend. Sawada, 1982)

Cobitidae (Swainson, 1839)

Sabanejewia (Vladykov, 1929)

23. *Sabanejewia aralensis* (Kessler, 1877)

Balitoridae (Swainson, 1839)

Nemacheilinae (Regan, 1911)

Nemacheilini (Swainson, 1839) (emend. nov.)

Iskandaria (Prokofiev, 2009)

24. *Iskandaria kuschakewitschi* (Herzenstein, 1890)

Triplophysini (Prokofiev 2010)

Triplophysa (Rendahl, 1933)

25. *Triplophysa coniptera* (Turdakov, 1954) *ssp. salari* (Turdakov 1954)

26. *Triplophysa dorsalis* (Kessler, 1872)

27. *Triplophysa elegans* (Kessler, 1874)

28. *Triplophysa strauchi* (Kessler, 1874)

Siluriformes

Ictaluridae (Gill, 1861)

Ictalurus (Rafinesque, 1820)

28. *Ictalurus punctatus* (Rafinesque, 1818)

Siluridae (Cuvier, 1816)

Silurus (Linnaeus, 1758)

30. *Silurus glanis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Sisoridae (Regan, 1911)

Glyptosterninae

Glyptosternon (McClelland, 1842)

31. *Glyptosternon oschanini* (Herzenstein, 1889)

Protacanthopterygii

Esociformes

Esocidae (Cuvier, 1816)

Esox (Linnaeus, 1758)

32. *Esox lucius* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Salmoniformes

Coregonidae (Cope, 1872)

Coregonus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Leucichthys (Dybowski, 1874)

33. *Coregonus peled* (Gmelin, 1789)

Salmonidae (Cuvier, 1816)

Parasalmo (Vladykov, 1972)

34. *Parasalmo mykiss* (Walbaum, 1792)

Salmo (Linnaeus, 1758)

35. *Salmo ischchan* (Kessler, 1877)

Acanthopterygii

Beloniformes

Adrianichthyidae

Oryzias (Jordan et Snyder, 1907)

36. *Oryzias sinensis* (Chen, Uwa et Chu, 1989)

Cyprinodontiformes

Cyprinodontoidei

Poeciliidae (Swainson, 1839)

Gambusia (Poey, 1854)

37. *Gambusia affinis* (Baird and Girard, 1853)

38. *Gambusia holbrooki* (Girard, 1859)

Scorpaeniformes

Cottoidei

Cottidae (Bonaparte, 1831)

Cottinae (Bonaparte, 1831)

Cottus (Linnaeus, 1758)

39. *Cottus jaxartensis* (Berg, 1916)

Perciformes

Percoidei

Percidae (Cuvier, 1816)

Sander (Oken, 1817)

40. *Sander lucioperca* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Gobioidei

Odontobutidae (Hoesse et Gill, 1993)

Micropercops (Fowler et Bean, 1920)

41. *Micropercops cinctus* (Dabry de Thiersant, 1872)

Gobiidae (Fleming, 1822)

Rhinogobius (Gill, 1859)

42. *Rhinogobius brunneus* (Temminck et Schlegel, 1845)

Channoidei

Channidae (Fowler, 1934)

Channa (Scopoli, 1777)

43. *Channa argus* (Cantor, 1842)

Conclusion: thus, the modern ichthyofauna of the Chirchik River (including the Charvak reservoir) has 43 species belonging to 38 genera, 15 families, 8 orders. Of these, 25 are native, 18 are invasive (acclimatized and accidentally introduced).

In the data of Salikhov (**Salikhov, 1990**), 39 species were mentioned in the ichthyofauna of the Chirchik River, including: 11 acclimatized, 9 accidental and 19 local species.

According to Wundtsettel (**Wundzettel, 2006**), 37 species are listed in the modern ichthyofauna of the Chirchik River.

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